

APPLICATIONS OF NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING BASED ON PRIVACY-PRESERVING FEDERATED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a branch of machine learning that assists companies in better representing their internal knowledge through data structure optimisation. Natural language processing models should be appropriately protected to facilitate their re-use in different settings. So, the issue of what privacy-preserving technology (PET) is best becomes relevant. This suggests that it's best to refrain from using a server to train a model because it's undesirable. While the Federated Learning (FL) method can be useful in certain cases, it is not a panacea, particularly where data privacy is at stake. An FL framework that preserves privacy is shown here for input expression in collaborative ML model training, which makes use of bitwise quantization, local differential privacy (LDP), and feature hashing. Quantifying the local model updates is the initial step of our strategy. Then, we apply a randomized-response methodology to the resulting update vector. We showcase the method's efficacy with natural language processing data, but it is adaptable enough to handle any type of input attributes. A rolling hash representation encrypts the client-side text, which eliminates the need to share sensitive information and the resource requirements of embedding methods. We tested our method on two datasets: one containing sentiment analysis tasks from IMDB Movie Reviews and the other containing rating prediction tasks from MovieLens datasets enhanced with additional movie keywords. Our solution offers a viable alternative to resource-intensive language models and data collection practices that end users are concerned about when it comes to private language processing on edge devices.

Keywords: Privacy Techniques, Natural Language Processing, NLP, PET

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INTRODUCTION

Natural Language Processing, also referred to as NLP, is an area of machine learning that focuses on the capacity of computers to perceive, analyse, modify, and possibly even synthesise human language [1]. NLP is sometimes referred to as English Language Processing. NLP, which stands for natural language processing, is gaining popularity as a result of the extensive variety of applications it offers in the field of text analysis. On the other hand, because natural language processing algorithms can identify and replicate the unique aspects of a person's communication habits, it opens the door to extremely sophisticated attacks [2]. This opens the door for very complex assaults to be launched by a single person. Natural language processing (NLP) is fraught with several significant difficulties. Among these challenges is the ability to identify genuine speech, understand spoken natural language, and, finally, produce reasonable natural language. Furthermore, safeguarding individuals' privacy is a major concern when it comes to training sensitive information [3]. There is a monetary and labour cost associated with training these models. For these models to be useful in a variety of settings in the future, it is essential that private data can be recovered from them.

This can only be achieved if these models are compatible with the privacy-guaranteeing technologies, or PET. The goal of this research is to survey the existing literature on the topic of natural language processing (NLP) privacy protection in order to lay the framework for future research. A comprehensive analysis of all existing privacy-protecting technology implementations is beyond the scope of this research. Data privacy in NLP is an interdisciplinary field, which is why this is the case. All of the ways that people express themselves verbally, in writing, or through visual means are collectively known as "natural language processing" (NLP). In the last several years, machine learning (ML) has found a home in almost every aspect of our lives, and its applications have grown increasingly pervasive. Many different industries have a plethora of attractive potential uses. Numerous image processing apps for mobile devices, chatbots and other AI agents used in public administration, healthcare diagnostics, and many more instances of such applications are just a few examples. The growing value of personal information has prompted stringent regulatory requirements, such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹ [4].

But many ML systems rely on secret, protected, or classified information that should not be shared with any data curator, no matter how reliable they are [5]. In contrast, personalised machine learning apps use this information to glean accurate and exact knowledge from user input during training. A possible workaround for this issue could be for users to retain data locally on their end and train models at the edges of the network.

The Federated Learning (FL) approach [6] merely transmits the local model updates without ever exposing the server to the raw training data. It is on this fundamental idea that the FL technique is built. The proliferation of edge devices, including mobile phones, IoT technologies, and smart home devices, necessitates the ongoing development of distributed and decentralised training approaches. A common use of FL is the training of a shared global model across several nodes. Many businesses use it because they either do not want to or are unable to share data on a local level [7]. For instance, in a healthcare setting, the participating institutions can use patient data stored locally to train the global model.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram for a centralised four-stage workflow in a FL framework.

This research focuses on a centralised FL, where all training aspects are organised by a single server or service provider. It is the job of this coordination server to do the following tasks: steps: the first step is to select a global model to train, the second is to select local nodes to participate in training, the third is to gather training results from all the nodes, the fourth is to update the global model, the fifth is to share the updated model with the nodes, and the sixth is to stop training when the model satisfies certain criteria, like being accurate enough. By actively responding to requests with their own data, the local nodes train the model. They promptly communicate their findings to the server once it is practical to do so. The four-stage workflow cycle in a centralised FL framework is illustrated in Figure 1:

1. **Participant Selection and Global Model Dissemination:** Only those who meet the criteria will be chosen by the server to take part in the training. After then, it moves on to the training phase, when it updates the global machine learning model and distributes it among the participants.
2. **Local Computation:** On behalf of the participants, the server selects those individuals who are eligible to take part in the training process after determining that they meet the necessary requirements. After the training is complete, it will provide the participants with a global machine learning model or updates to that model. This will take place during the subsequent phase.
3. **Local Models Aggregation:** In order to update the global machine learning model, the server will wait until it has received enough locally trained models from the participants. Proceed with this as the subsequent stage. This aggregation process needs to integrate many privacy-preserving mechanisms, including safe aggregation, differential privacy, and advanced encryption approaches, to ensure that the server cannot independently check the parameters of the machine learning model.
4. **Global Model Update:** Step 3 involved collecting aggregated model parameters. The server would then update the presently employed global machine learning model based on these parameters. Following the completion of the subsequent training session, participants will be provided with this revised global model.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to [8], data privacy is a subset of data security that includes all parts of data management, such as data collecting, storage, and the topic of sharing data with third parties. Information privacy and data privacy are interchangeable terms. While reviewing the literature, we are primarily interested in four methods: anonymization, Differential Privacy (DP), Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), and homomorphic encryption.

Federated Learning (FL) is also a focus of our attention.

For this particular research project, we chose SMPC and HE since our objective was to broaden the scope of our findings by examining not only approaches for anonymization but also strategies that are based on cryptography. FL was chosen because it protects individuals' privacy during the process of data collection and processing, and it does not wait to be applied solely to the outcomes of the study. DP is a technique that is based on perturbation and is one of the most recently introduced PET techniques. It was selected due to its ability to measure the degree of privacy that is retained through the utilisation of a magical number known as Epsilon(ϵ). The following is a concise introduction of the techniques that were chosen.

FL: Within the context of the process of constructing a prediction model, FL is a technique to machine learning that is decentralised. using the use of FL, the owner of the data is able to train a shared prediction model using collaborative learning without having to hand over the data to a computer that they do not have control over. This allows the owner to keep ownership of the data. "Bringing the code to the data, instead of the data to the code" is the general strategy that FL takes in order to work, and it aims to solve the important issues of data ownership, privacy, and locality [9].

Anonymization: Anonymization is the process of automatically detecting and eliminating or changing sensitive information from a text document. Names, sensitive terms, and numbers (such as credit card numbers) fall into this category. A term for this procedure is "anonymization." The goal of this approach is to protect the sensitive data while yet making the text usable for analysis [10].

DP: For further information, see [11]. Dwork, Dinur, Nassim, Smith, and others first proposed DP, and it has subsequently undergone several extensions, such as in [12]. In [13], Desfontaines and Pejo present a comprehensive taxonomy of DP that is particularly complex. With DP, you can be confident that the presence of any person will not significantly affect the delivery of any database study. An adversary would have a hard time retrieving a single row of data due to this. At its core, this method revolves around the idea of indistinguishability, which is fundamental to semantic security. Some argue that the value of ϵ indicates how much privacy protection is needed, and it also affects how useful or accurate this privacy method is. The privacy protection is stronger when the values of ϵ are smaller. This is due to the fact that in reality, none of the input data from any one 'X' is ever used to generate the output, so simulating the circumstance is the most realistic option. The level of precision is lower when the ϵ value is lower [14].

SMPC: An other method of cryptography is known as SMPC. Multiple parties are able to conduct a collaborative computation on a sequence of inputs through the use of SMPC, which provides them with the ability to conceal their own input [15]. As a result of the collaboration of numerous parties, computations are carried out based on each individual's private data [16]. There is a function $f(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ that they compute. All the values $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ are considered to be private, whereas the result $\alpha = f(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ is disclosed to all individuals. For the purpose of ensuring that the input of all parties remains private, secret sharing is utilised [17]. It is the responsibility of each partner to reveal a certain amount of her secret to the other partners during the sharing phase. The computing step makes use of addition and multiplication, two secure operations. When dealing with two secrets, the conditions that would apply are addition and

multiplication, respectively, where each party adds their share of the secrets locally and each party multiplies their share of the secrets by each other. As a result, additional computations make the partnership possible. When the reconstruction stage is complete, the parties will divulge their respective shares of the function value in order for everyone to acquire this knowledge (see also [18]).

Many natural language processing (NLP) tasks have been greatly improved by pre-trained language models (PLMs) in recent years. These include text classification, answering questions, sentiment analysis, information retrieval, and summarization, among many others [19]. A number of these models are very new, but they are already attracting a lot of attention. Just one example: OpenAI's ChatGPT now has more than 180 million users [20]. Additional well-liked advanced models include LLaMA by Meta, OPT and OPT-IML, and BLOOM and BLOOMZ by BigScience [21]. The ability to prompt is one of the new features of LLMs. Without modifying the model parameters, an LLM can be instructed in natural language and given examples to predict the results of a query by prompting. Direct prompts, often called zero-shots, are the simplest kind of prompts. In these, users pose the instruction as a question and don't supply the LLM any examples. Another kind of prompting that has been suggested alongside GPT-3 [22] is in-context learning (ICL), which incorporates a few examples of demonstration into the prompt. By utilizing pre-trained or customized LLMs, ICL efficiently and effectively handles several downstream jobs without modifying the model parameters for each task.

Universal pre-trained language models (PLMs) using self-supervised learning techniques have been developed by the academic community in response to the proliferation of large unlabeled datasets and the success of Transformers [23, 24]. To differentiate PLMs from LLMs, which are defined by huge parameter sizes (tens or hundreds of billions of parameters), the word "LLMs" is used. A LLM's capacity to understand and effectively produce natural languages is honed via pre-training on large corpora.

A new learning paradigm, ICL is an example of a prompting method [25] that allows LLMs to make predictions using just a small number of demonstration instances to illustrate various scenarios. Prompts in ICL are textual descriptions of tasks and/or examples of demonstrations given in a natural language format. Learning via analogy is important to in-context learning. Figure 2 is a representation of ICL.

Figure 2: An illustration of ICL. In ICL, the prompt consists of a task description (light green), demonstration examples (light blue), and a query (light orange).

Applications of Natural Language Processing Based on Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning

The query is often prepared in natural language templates and then attached to the demonstration examples. After that, the task description, examples of the demonstration, and the inquiry are sent to a distant LLM, which is typically located in the cloud. It is believed that the LLM will be able to deduce the hidden patterns from the demonstration and instantly produce the prediction without updating the parameters. Contrast this with supervised learning, which often employs backward gradients to modify model parameters during the training phase. You may guide the LLM to provide the right response by providing it with suitable demonstration instances. Let $D_k = \{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_k, y_k)\}$ represent a set of k instances used for presentation. A formal formulation of the following function, $b(x_k, y_k)$, which is used to convert the k -th demonstration example into natural language text from LLMs:

$$LLM(\text{inst}, \underbrace{g(x_1, y_1), \dots, g(x_k, y_k)}_{\text{demonstration examples}}, \underbrace{g(x_{k+1}, \text{query})}_{\text{query}}, \text{answer}) \rightarrow \hat{y}_{k+1}$$

How well ICL works is largely dependent on how well the prompts are constructed, and on how to choose the right instances for presentation. Since both ICL and instruction tuning make use of natural language to build tasks and instances, there is an intrinsic relationship between the two. In contrast to ICL, which just stimulates LLMs for utilization, instruction tuning requires fine-tuning LLMs for adaptation. Readers interested in a thorough analysis of ICL are encouraged to peruse the survey study [27]. Several types of data have been used to study FL's potential in the mental health sector, where it has been used to treat disorders like bipolar disorder, depression, schizophrenia, suicidal ideation, and other associated issues.[28] Because of its abundance in many different places, textual data is quickly becoming the most popular kind of information in the field of mental health. Therapists' notes, patient-therapist communications, therapy sessions, patient-authored content in online communities for health and medicine, and electronic health records are all examples of such sources. The assumption that the data are geographically monolingual, homogenous, or at least have overlapping distributions among clients limited prior research on natural language processing (NLP) with FL in the mental health area [29].

The use of FL in a multilingual setting to diagnose mental health issues, however, is a relatively new development.¹⁵ A variety of language tasks have lately investigated multilingual FL because it offers a fascinating and natural environment in which to analyze non-IID data, of which several languages are an apparent use [30]. The use of DL methods has recently contributed to NLP advancements, with outstanding results achieved for tasks like automatic question-answering, dependency parsing, machine translation, text classification, word sense disambiguation, and natural language understanding. Nevertheless, in situations where there is more than one compute party involved in the learning process or when the data is outsourced, DL models that are trained or used to draw conclusions from sensitive text data could be vulnerable to privacy risks. As a result, protecting sensitive information is a top priority when designing natural language processing (NLP) applications [31].

The processing expenditures that PETs may demand, in addition to the difficulty of recognizing sensitive qualities in text, make it a formidable obstacle to protecting text data privacy. Removing personal characteristics doesn't always prevent them from drawing conclusions from their environment. One example is the practice of placing place names next to descriptions that make them easy to recognize. A vast body of independent literature has emerged as an active area of study in response to numerous privacy-related problems in natural language processing. Despite its breadth, privacy-preserving natural language processing literature fails to offer a clear classification of methods pertaining to DL and PETs, which would help academics and professionals in the field have a better grasp of the key issues and technologies [32].

Table 1: Overview of related surveys on privacy for DL and NLP

Work	Year	Contributions
Technical privacy metrics: A systematic survey [33]	2018	Information about 80+ privacy measures, their classification, theoretical underpinnings, application domains, contextual examples, and a methodology to find the right metrics for the right situations in the real world.
Mitigating gender bias in natural language processing: Literature review [34]	2019	An analysis of current literature on the topic of algorithmic gender bias in natural language processing (NLP), with the goal of identifying strengths, weaknesses, and research needs in this area.
Text analysis in adversarial settings: Does deception leave a stylistic trace? [35]	2019	Investigation of stylistic shifts as a means of identifying misleading prose, evaluation of the extent to which authorship identification methods incorporate privacy risks, account of attack contexts, description of style obfuscation and imitation techniques, and debate regarding the traceability of such techniques.
A survey on interdependent privacy [36]	2019	Observations on privacy and interdependent privacy, drawing attention to the many ways in which the scientific community approaches these issues; an examination of research instruments and theoretical frameworks; and a classification of potential threats, issues, and remedies.
A review of privacy-preserving techniques for deep learning [37]	2020	Analyzing the performance of privacy-preserving approaches for DL, followed by a taxonomy with multiple levels.
The AI-based cyber threat landscape: A survey [38]	2020	The plot of cyberattacks using AI methods onto a system for the categorization of unethical AI applications. Also, this effort lays the groundwork for future events to be able to detect them. Additionally, a smart grid infrastructure attack scenario is provided to demonstrate the proposed framework in action.
Adversarial attacks on deep learning models in natural language processing: A survey [39]	2020	A survey, analysis, and classification of research on adversarial example generation for natural language processing (NLP) applications using DL models.

Many factors, including privacy measurements, DL models, natural language processing jobs, dangers, computing scenarios, and PETs, contribute to the protection of privacy. Attempting to unite these disparate viewpoints, this piece occupies a space where they meet. So, to give a comprehensive overview of the privacy-preserving DL methods for NLP and to highlight the potential privacy difficulties with NLP data, we survey the literature on privacy, DL, and NLP from 2016 to 2020.

The following topics have been covered in recent survey studies: privacy-preserving DL, security attacks, security difficulties, biases in NLP, privacy on social media, adversarial threats in text data, and privacy metrics. Table 1 displays the titles of these papers. Apart from a comprehensive unified assessment for natural language processing (NLP) applications built on deep learning (DL) models, each of the works in the table presents a unique angle on privacy preservation. To further emphasize our review's thoroughness, the publications we examined seldom overlap with those in Table 1.

METHODOLOGY

Connected RR-LDP Algorithm 2 shows what happens on the client side of our FL framework, whereas Algorithm 1 shows what happens on the server side. Our current federated learning system relies on local devices receiving model parameters from the server.

They then proceed to update the model using the local data as they normally would. No data interaction between clients occurs at any point in time because our framework is built to fit to a horizontal FL architecture, as mentioned previously.

$$\forall x \in \mathbf{R}^d : P[Q(D) = x] \leq e^\epsilon \cdot P[Q(D') = x], \quad (1)$$

In Algorithm 2, after a quantization step (line 8) and an LDP privatisation (line 9), clients report the updated parameter sets relative to the original ones (line 7 after the local update). Since the parameter values are proportional to the learning rate, computing the differences enables us to readily control their amounts. To achieve the change indicated in equation (3) and convert the values to the set $\{0, 1\}$, a probabilistic quantization is performed to the discrepancies in the parameters.

Algorithm 1 Server

```

1:  $\Theta_0, q, \epsilon \leftarrow \text{initialize}()$ 
2: loop  $t=0, 1, \dots$ 
3:   for every node  $i$  do
4:     send  $(\Theta_t, q, \epsilon)$  to  $i$ 
5:     receive  $[\Delta_i]$  from  $i$ 
6:   wait()
7:    $[\tilde{\Delta}] \leftarrow \sum_{i \in K} \frac{|N_i|}{|N|} [\tilde{\Delta}_i]$ 
8:    $[\Delta] \leftarrow \text{correction}([\tilde{\Delta}])$ 
9:    $\Delta \leftarrow \text{dequantize}([\Delta])$ 
10:   $\Theta_{t+1} \leftarrow \Theta_t + \Delta$ 

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Algorithm 2 Client (at device i)

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1:  $\text{data}_i$ : local data on device  $i$ 
2:  $x_h \leftarrow \text{hash\_text}(\text{data}_i)$ 
3:  $x_e \leftarrow \text{extract\_feature}(\text{data}_i)$ 
4:  $x_i \leftarrow [x_h, x_e]$   $\triangleright x_e$  is optional
5: procedure ONRECEIVE( $\Theta_t, q, \epsilon$ )
6:    $\Theta_{t+1}^i \leftarrow \text{update}(\Theta_t, x_i)$ 
7:    $\Delta_i \leftarrow \Theta_{t+1}^i - \Theta_t$ 
8:    $[\tilde{\Delta}_i] \leftarrow \text{quantize}(\Delta_i, q)$ 
9:    $[\tilde{\Delta}_i] \leftarrow \text{randomize}([\tilde{\Delta}_i], \epsilon)$ 
10:  send( $[\tilde{\Delta}_i]$ )

```

$$\forall x \in \mathbf{R}^d : P[Q(v) = x] \leq e^\epsilon \cdot P[Q(v') = x], \quad (2)$$

$$[v] = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{with probability } (q - v)/2q \\ 1 & \text{with probability } (v + q)/2q. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Regarding the vector $[-0.154, 0.761, \dots, -0.433]$, let us use it as an example. To ensure that the vector components are compressed to the interval $[-0.5, 0.5]$, the quantization range, q , is set to 0.5 . The result is a clipped vector with the values $[-0.154, 0.500, \dots, -0.433]$. An example of a binary vector with the values $[1, 1, \dots, 0]$ can be obtained by applying the probability value from (3) to a probabilistic binary quantization step. After the bits in the binary vector are flipped according to the fourth equation, the remaining vector $[1, 0, \dots, 0]$ is eventually delivered back to the network server. Additionally, this method offers a naturally occurring low upload bandwidth, which is great because the parameter vector values are still binary.

During the server-side process, the parameters that have been received are averaged in order to obtain an estimate of the actual update step. Prior to implementing the update, it is essential to remove the bias caused by the randomised response and de-quantize the values to their initial range.

Fig. 3. Federated Learning Architectures

A learning method called "federated learning" allows users, sometimes called clients or nodes, to exchange models and benefit from them without storing all of the training data in one place. On the flip side, clients save their own data locally and use it to update a server-managed global model. The parameters that make up a neural network are one such example.

The latter is responsible for orchestrating the clients and receiving updates from them. This definition describes a centralised learning architecture that is referred to as "Centralised Federated Learning" (CFL). To create a global model from the locally computed changes, this design requires a server.

The decentralised learning architecture is an alternative to the traditional centralised learning architecture (CFL). This design eliminates the need for a central server by allowing nearby clients to aggregate local model parameters. The clients are able to communicate with one another through a variety of network topologies that are provided by this "Decentralised Federated Learning" architecture (DFL). Some examples of these include Ring, Fully-Connected, Star, Random, and Node Clustering. Figure 3 shows that the particular use case scenario determines the applicability of each of them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 4. Analysing the results of the central and federated RR-LDP tests on the datasets with different amounts of clients (N).

For the IMDB dataset, see Figure 4, and for the MovieLens dataset, see Tables 2 and 3, respectively, which display the AUC-based results from the FL models. It is possible to compare these findings with the other datasets. The results show that the models are merging as the number of client devices increases. In the absence of a privacy protection phase, the centralised baseline model produced results that are in accord with those of the FL-trained models.

According to the data presented in Table 1 and the chart at the top of Figure 3, using only ten nodes is not sufficient to achieve the requisite level of accuracy and convergence. The comparatively significant variation that happens when not enough models' parameters are averaged on the server side is likely the cause of this instability. Also, occasionally, when using a bigger number of edge devices ($N = 250$), both datasets end up with models that are marginally less accurate. The identical hyperparameters set for all FL settings is the root cause of this issue, which is a result of a design decision we made. It means that we maintained a consistent learning rate, communication rounds, and, most crucially, local batch size to ensure an equal quantity of updates. Since the training data is spread evenly among all of the clients, the local learning batches will get smaller as the number of clients grows.

This holds true even if Figure 3 shows that models converge even for the biggest networks with 250 clients. But in this case, it's possible that some accuracy will be lost. This drop in performance suggests that there is a minimum allowable amount of customer data for training purposes. Results are not as reliable when less data is used than this level. One possible remedy to this issue is to increase the amount of data utilised for training.

Table 2. Findings from the IMDB Movie Reviews datasets applied with the federated RR-LDP approach, with varying values of N and R, the number of communication rounds. .

R	Number of clients			
	N = 10	N = 50	N = 100	N = 250
1	0.586	0.558	0.724	0.570
5	0.789	0.699	0.810	0.814
10	0.841	0.836	0.847	0.854
15	0.869	0.872	0.875	0.879
20	0.889	0.895	0.899	0.899
25	0.898	0.909	0.911	0.911
30	0.899	0.913	0.916	0.915
40	0.894	0.916	0.919	0.919
50	0.885	0.915	0.918	0.918
<i>Central</i>	<i>0.923</i>			

Table 3. Results obtained from the MovieLens 1M datasets using the federated RR-LDP method with different values for the client count (N) and the number of communication rounds (R). Areas under the curve (AUCs) are all stated.

R	Number of clients			
	N = 10	N = 50	N = 100	N = 250
1	0.695	0.682	0.649	0.552
5	0.717	0.716	0.711	0.644
10	0.722	0.720	0.716	0.681
15	0.723	0.722	0.720	0.699
20	0.724	0.724	0.722	0.707
25	0.725	0.726	0.723	0.709
30	0.727	0.726	0.725	0.712
40	0.728	0.728	0.727	0.715
50	0.729	0.729	0.728	0.718
<i>Central</i>	<i>0.730</i>			

The performance and convergence of the training operation are impacted by two components of our privacy-preserving FL framework. Introduced in (3), the quantization parameter q is one such example. In order to convert the model parameters into binary numbers that can be sent to the server, it is necessary to define the scale. The results of our federated RR-LDP method are shown in Figure 5 and Tables 3 and 4, along with a range of quantization ranges. Note that the two separate datasets have different q ranges. It is evident that this value has an impact on performance; in order to maximise efficiency, the quantization parameter must be brought close to the learning rate. By selecting a large value for q , it is feasible to "hide" the information that was quantized and encoded into the model parameters.

However, the quantization procedure "clips" the data when chosen values that are too little. The results show, however, that by incorporating more edge devices into federated training, this information loss can be mitigated. Testing different values for q may be necessary to find the optimal one, since this parameter's optimal value depends on factors including the model's architecture, the rate of learning, and the dataset presently being used. Selecting a value for q that is the same magnitude as the learning rate parameter is a solid general rule of thumb. This would be accurate if the relevant feature set's values fell within the interval $[0, 1]$. We have set the privacy parameter to 10 in order to do these tests, which leads to an incredibly low perturbation ratio and a significantly compromised level of privacy.

Fig. 5. Performance of the federated RR-LDP as a function of quantization range (q) for varying client numbers (N).

Based on the supplied number of clients (N), **Table 4** shows how the quantization range (q) affects the performance of the federated RR-LDP. You can find all of the results, including the AUCs, in the IMDB Movie Reviews dataset.

q	Number of clients			
	$N = 10$	$N = 50$	$N = 100$	$N = 250$
0.01	0.678	0.727	0.757	0.792
0.001	0.860	0.877	0.886	0.887
0.0001	0.887	0.903	0.900	0.891
0.00001	0.801	0.882	0.888	0.875
<i>Central</i>	0.923			

Table 5. Performance of the federated RR-LDP as a function of quantization range (q) for varying client numbers (N). The AUCs for the MovieLens 1M dataset are used for all values.

q	Number of clients			
	$N = 10$	$N = 50$	$N = 100$	$N = 250$
1.0	0.665	0.699	0.702	0.699
0.1	0.721	0.723	0.725	0.718
0.01	0.730	0.730	0.729	0.712
0.001	0.731	0.730	0.728	0.710
<i>Central</i>	0.730			

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this research was to offer a framework for FL that protects users' privacy and enables them to train machine learning models in a private setting using local data that is saved on a collection of client devices. A locally differentially private method based on randomised responses is used to update the local model. Our goal is to enhance the level of privacy protection for our clients. In particular, prior to being transmitted back for server-side aggregation, the weight discrepancies between the client and central server models are binary quantized and randomised. Prior to returning the discrepancies to the client, this is completed. Our primary research focus here was on NLP-related use cases, where the client data was textual representations of natural languages. Having said that, our framework was built to be functional and packed with features. For textual feature extraction on the client's end, we employ a vocabulary-free, low-cost text embedding technique based on the polynomial rolling hash algorithm. For even more efficient privacy protection in our system, we hash the user's local text input directly on their devices. This is because the hash function only converts in one direction, making the inversion process computationally challenging. By applying our proposed private federated learning technique to a small number of text-feature-based example classification tasks, we were able to show that the accuracy loss was minimal. Each individual component that makes up our structure offers a number of advantages. To be more specific, the hash representation makes it possible to embed text with low storage requirements, has a low computational complexity, and does not require any specialised language models. Additionally, it makes it simple to incorporate textual features into the proposed private federated learning technique. In terms of our approach to user privacy protection, the randomised response method guarantees local differential privacy and uses low-cost bitwise vectors to alleviate communication strain during data transfer phases between clients and servers.

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Applications of Natural Language Processing Based on Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning

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